

NOVEL EPOXY NANO COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

This paper describes the use of Ytterbium triflate as a latent curing agent and nano modified epoxy resins to produce polymer matrices with enhanced physical properties. Ytterbium triflate is a novel curing system and little research has been previously published on the use of this system to achieve cure of epoxy resins. A study of the cure behaviour, using the Strathclyde curometer is reported. It is shown that rapid cure can be initiated over a relatively narrow temperature window of 90⁰ to 120⁰C which is accessible for many composite applications. The gelation time is also found to be sensitive to the concentration of the catalyst present in the resin. The incorporation of nano particles, created using a sol gel approach, allows enhancement of the physical properties of the base resin matrix. Incorporation of γ -valerolactone into the cure system influences the rate at which cure occurs and the physical properties of the matrix formed. The mechanical and thermal properties of the materials were studied using dynamic mechanical thermal analysis and differential scanning calorimetry. The incorporation of the γ -valerolactone at certain levels leads to a reduction of the glass transition temperature with increasing level of nano filler rather than the expected increase.

Keywords:- epoxy, ytterbium triflate, nanosilica, composite resins, dynamic mechanical thermal analysis, differential scanning calorimetry.

INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins used in many composite applications are cured using amine hardeners. In some electrical applications, cyanoguanidine or dicyandiamide is often used to produce a hard matrix material. An alternative latent curing system which has been used is the boron trifluoride:amine complex. This system is activated over a relatively broad temperature range and shows a number of problems when used to provide a one pot curing system. Recently, the use of Ytterbium triflate has been reported [1-3]. This system combined with γ -valerolactone presents an attractive alternative to boron trifluoride : amine complex as a latent curing system. Lewis acid catalysts such as boron trifluoride : amine complex are moisture sensitivity and have the potential to generate hydrogen fluoride. Lanthanide triflates have the advantage of being more moisture stable than Lewis acids. Lanthanide triflates have the advantage of the strong electron withdrawing capacity of the trifluoromethanesulfonate anion.

Improvements in mechanical properties of epoxy resins have been observed with the additional of nano scale fillers [4-12]. The nature of the effect depends on the nature of the filler; exfoliated platelets cause significant increase in the glass transition

temperature when there is a strong interaction between the resin and the filler, whereas improvements in the impact strength are observed with spherical particles. In this study we report a study on latent cured epoxy resins which contain a nano scale spherical reinforcement. The nano silica materials are obtained via a sol-gel process and have a size which is typically of the order of 20 nm. The sol-gel process allows the incorporation of various reactive functional groups into the surface. The nano silica used in this study have epoxy functionality.

EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 MATERIALS

The epoxy resin used in this study was based on Bisphenol F (PY306) obtained from Huntsman. A nano silica modified version of the resin – Nanopox A510 was supplied by Nanoresins. The nano modified resin contains 40wt% nanosilica with particles ~ 20 nm in size. Both the Ytterbium trifluorosulfonate (Yb triflate) and the γ -valerolactone were obtained from Aldrich Chemicals.

Samples were prepared as 10 g batches; the Yb triflate being added to the dried beaker and dissolved in acetone. The epoxy components were then added and the mixture thoroughly stirred and degassed to remove the acetone and air bubbles. Cure conditions were varied as indicated in the paper.

2.2 CURE MEASUREMENTS

Measurements of the change of the viscosity with time were obtained using the Strathclyde curometer [13]. The sample to be measured was held in an oil bath and contained in a small glass vial. The temperature of the oil bath and the sample were adjusted to that required for the measurement. The paddle probe was lowered into the sample and operated at a frequency of 2Hz and amplitude of ~500 μ m. The sensor output is the amplitude and phase of the probe motion which is directly related to the viscosity changes occurring in the sample. The data was recorded using Picolog software package. The gelation was taken as the point at which the viscosity of the material reaches a value of 10^4 Pas.

2.3 DYNAMIC MECHANICAL THERMAL ANALYSIS - DMTA

For DMTA measurements, moulded samples were prepared by curing the mixtures in an oven at 110°C for 12 hours. Small strips of dimensions 10 mm x 20 mm x ~1 mm were cut from the moulded pieces and used for the measurements which were performed using a Polymer Laboratories Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analyser MKIII, at a frequency of 1 Hz, a strain of x 4, scanning rate of 4°C per minute and the samples were clamped with a torque of 40 N. Knife edged clamping was employed, with a sample length of 5 mm. The bending modulus and $\tan \delta$ were measured over the temperature range of 25 to 150°C. The peak in the $\tan \delta$ curve was used to locate the glass transition temperature.

2.4 DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY – DSC

DSC measurements were performed using a TA Q1000 instrument. The sample weight was typically 4-6mg and measurements were made using a hermetical sealed aluminium pan. In general, a dynamic run was performed between -50°C and 250°C at a heating rate of 10°C min⁻¹. Isothermal scans were also carried out at the desired temperatures and typically involved observations over a period of 180 minutes. On completion of the isothermal scans, dynamic post cure measurements were made by firstly cooling to -50°C and then increasing at a rate of 10C min⁻¹ to 250°C min⁻¹. The

traces obtained were used in the usual way to investigate the extent of cure and identify the glass transition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON CURE

Only limited information exists on the use of Yb triflate as a curing agent for epoxy resins and it was therefore appropriate to investigate how temperature influenced the rate at which cure occurs. The initial study was carried out using 0.5 pph of Yb triflate and measurements were performed at 90°C, 100°C, 110°C, 120°C. It was noted that at temperatures above 100°C discolouration of the samples occurred and stress patterns were visible. Measurements of the cure profiles, figure (1), indicate that as the temperature is increased the rate of cure is correspondingly increased. The point at which the amplitude of the probe motion drops is indicative of the increase in the viscosity and the peak in the phase shift marks the point of maximum viscoelastic response, which is indicative of the gel formation in the system.

[A]

[B]

Figure (1) Curometer data for Yb triflate – DGEBF over the temperature range 90°C to 120°C; [A] amplitude variation, [B] phase variation.

The discoloration at the higher temperatures is attributed to the occurrence of the catalyst creating an excessive exotherm and inducing oxidation of the material. In a

number of cases the darkening occurred as spots, located around catalyst particles. Variation of the times to gelation are presented in table (1).

Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Gelation time (s)	Temperature($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Gelation Time (s)
90	21310	110	7750
100	11160	120	4090

Table (1) Variation with temperature of gelation times for DGEBF – 0.5 pph Yb triflate.

If it is assumed that the initiation step for the polymerization is thermally activated then a plot of the reciprocal of the gelation time against the reciprocal of the temperature should be a straight line with slope the activation energy divided by the gas constant. A value of the activation energy of $63 \pm 0.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ was obtained and is consistent with values of the activation energy obtained from infrared spectroscopic measurements reported by other workers [1,3]. In addition to temperature, catalyst concentration can have a significant effect on the rate of cure. To explore this effect measurements of the rate of cure were performed at 90°C with varying levels of the catalyst, figure (2).

[A]

[B]

Figure (2) Curometer data for Yb triflate – DGEBF at 90°C as a function of catalyst concentration variation between 1.0 and 0.3pph; [A] amplitude variation, [B] phase variation.

The values of the gelation time obtained at 90°C are presented in table (2).

Concentration of Yb triflate (pph)	Gelation time (s)	Concentration of Yb triflate (pph)	Gelation time (s)
1.0	48062	0.5	15554
0.6	29652	0.3	6650
0.5	21310		

Table (2) Variation of gelation time with Yb triflate concentration measured at 90°C.

A graph of the reciprocal of the gel time against Yb triflate concentration shows a linear slope. The problem of discoloration and the high rates of cure indicated that for pure epoxy satisfactory cure can be achieved at 90°C.

3.2 INCORPORATION OF NANO SILICA.

It has been shown [4-7] that the incorporation of nano silica can have a significant effect on increasing the impact strength of the resins. A study was undertaken in which varying ratios of the pure DGEBA and the DGEBA containing nano silica were mixed to produce compositions with varying silica content. Cure data for these systems are shown in Figure (3). The introduction of the epoxy functionalised nano silica leads to an acceleration of the cure process, reflected in the progressive shortening of the cure time with increase in the level of the silica nano particles present in the resin. The initial decrease in time to gelation observed with the addition of ~15% of silica does not continue as the level is increased further. The gelation times for the 20 to 40% loaded resins are all very similar, indicating that the reduction in cure time produced by the addition of silica is not maintained for higher loadings.

Figure (3) Variation of gelation time with silica content.

3.3 ADDITION OF γ VALEROLACTONE.

In composite applications it is desirable to reduce the shrinkage which occurs on cure. Incorporation of spiroorthocarbonates (SOCs) and bicycloorthoesters (BOEs) have been shown to reduce the contraction after gelation and therefore lower internal stresses in the cured resins. The reactions which occur are complex and illustrated in

figure (4). During the curing process four chemical processes are possible:(a) formation of SOE by reaction of DGEBF with γ -lactone, (b) homo-polymerization of epoxy groups, (c) homo-polymerization of SOE, and (d) copolymerization of SOE with epoxy groups.

Figure (4) Possible reaction pathways for the reaction of γ -valerolactone with DGEBF.

Because SOEs homopolymerize or copolymerize with some expansion in the final stages of the curing, the contraction after gelation is reduced. Thus, the main contraction is produced when the material is a viscous liquid and in this way the internal stresses are reduced. Knowledge of the times to gelation can allow estimation of the times necessary to complete the cure processes and minimize shrinkage and the stresses generated in the thermoset on cure. Three levels of γ -valerolactone [VAL] addition were investigated. The addition of the VAL has the added advantage of lowering the viscosity of the resin mix and making degassing easier to perform. The gel times for the different ratios of DGEBF to VAL with varying silica levels are presented in table (3).

% Nano silica	Gel times (seconds)		
	3:1 VAL	2:1 VAL	1:1 VAL
0	4090	4600	4940
5	3520	4300	4000
10	2800	2800	3430
20	2400	2000	1650
30	2180	1300	1200
40	2000	1200	600

Table (3) Variation of the gelation times with the addition of γ -valerolactone and silica content.

As was observed with the study of the additional of the silica nano particles to the resin, a reduction in the gelation time is observed with increase in the silica content up to a level of addition of ~ 20%, where upon the gel time becomes approximately constant and is only reduced by a relatively small amount for further silica addition. Studies of the kinetics of related reactions between γ -lactones and epoxy resins have shown that γ -lactones are not able to homopolymerise and its incorporation involves the formation of SOE's (intermediate). The activation energy for the polymerization of the SOE is significantly lower than that for ring opening of the epoxy group with the effect that this is the preferred reaction. During the polymerization process the γ -lactone is consumed forming the SOE and the activation energy changes with the degree of conversion. The SOE will tend to expand the matrix which is formed and it is only after gelation that densification occurs. As a consequence it is found that shrinkage is reduced relative to that observed for the simple cure of the epoxy resin.

4.0 DYNAMIC MECHANICAL THERMAL ANALYSIS – DMTA AND DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY - DSC– DMTA.

DMTA samples were created by moulding the reaction mixtures used in the cure studies. Test strips were cut from the cured plaques and measurements performed between 30 and 160⁰C. The peak in the tan δ plot was used to identify the location of the glass transition – T_g . An example of the DMTA plots for 1:1 VAL cured with 0.6 pph Yb triflate are shown in figure (5). Increase in the silica content for the 1:1 VAL mixtures leads to a decrease in the value of T_g , figure (6). Normally, the addition of silica increases the value of T_g as the incorporation of the functionalised nano particles induces densification of the matrix. It is however apparent that when a high level of the VAL the SOE polymerization will predominate and a flexible open matrix will be created which leads to a lowering of the T_g . The observed continual reduction of the T_g with increasing nano silica content implies that the reaction of the VAL with the surface epoxy groups creates a matrix which is unable to undergo the usual densification which leads to the higher vales of the T_g observed in the pure resins. For the 3:1 VAL ratio however the lowering of the T_g is not observed, figure (6). The T_g peak remains almost constant and does not vary with change of silica content. It should however be noted that the values of the bending modulus measured above T_g shows a progressive increase with the addition of the silica. The modulus in the rubbery phase is a direct indication of the cross link density of the matrix. It is clear from the data that although the T_g is not being increased by the addition of the functionalised silica particles, the cross link density of the matrix is being modified. It may be inferred that the surface epoxy functions are incorporated in the polymerization before gelation and they inhibit further densification. However since the epoxy groups are tied into the rigid silica matrix the effect is to create a stable point of cross linking. In the case of the 1:1 VAL systems the increased flexibility arising from the SOE homopolymerization leads to a softer matrix. The variation of the T_g for the three systems studied are summarised in figure (7). Increase in the VAL content in the resin leads to a reduction in the value of the T_g from a value of ~110⁰C to a value of ~80⁰C with the 1:1: Val resins system, reflecting the plasticizing effect of the bridging ester containing elements associated with the polymerization of the SOE.

[A]

[B]

Figure (5) Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis data for 1:1 mixtures of VAL: DGEBF with varying nano silica content; [A] $\tan \delta$ [B] modulus.

[A]

[B]

Figure (6) Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Analysis data for 3:1 mixtures of VAL: DGEBF with varying nano silica content; [A] $\tan \delta$ [B] modulus.

Figure (7) Variation of the T_g with addition of nano silica content for various mixtures containing VAL: epoxy ratios. \blacklozenge 1:1 VAL, \blacksquare 2:1 Val, \blacktriangle 3:1 VAL.

Reduction of the VAL content in the case of the 2:1 and 3:1 mixtures leads to the observation that the T_g is apparently independent of the nano silica content. Inspection of the variation of the modulus above the T_g indicates that the addition of the silica nano particles has increased the value of the high temperature modulus which is

consistent with the particles being cross linked into the matrix. The implication is that the cross linking action of the nano silica is compensated by the flexibility introduced by the VAL.

CONCLUSIONS

The VAL has the positive effect of reducing the viscosity of the mixture and allowing the incorporation of the nano silica into an epoxy resin which is cured using the very effective Ytterbium triflate curing agent. The reactivity of the surface epoxy groups on the nano silica must be sufficiently high that the nano silica particles are incorporated in the matrix prior to gelation and hence able in the 1:1 system to reduce the T_g and in the case of the 2:1 and 3:1 to inhibit the densification process. The VAL is therefore demonstrating the expected ability to suppress the gelation and reduce shrinkage.

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